

Digital Banking in India

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Abstract

The banking system in the country has become so technologically advanced that almost all banking services are delivered through electronic platforms. Digital banking as a new business model, offered through multiple integrated channels of electronic banking services is the future of every banking sector in a century when technological innovation knows no bounds. The challenge of the banking sector in India remains the use of electronic banking services by customers. This paper covers role of digitization in Indian banking, factors affect the scope of digital banking in India, Challenges faced by the users of Digital Banking services in India, benefit of digital banking and Innovation of digital banking in India.

Key words: Digital Banking , Innovations Technology

Introduction

Digital banking is the use of the internet, mobile phones, and other electronic mediums as a delivery channel for banking services, which includes all traditional services such as balance enquiry, printing statement, fund transfer to other accounts, bills payment and new banking services such as electronic bill presentment and payment without necessarily visiting a bank. The invention of ATMs and credit cards paved the way for the digitization of the banks. The commercial evolution of the internet in the early 1990s completely overhauled the banking sector introducing the world to the online banking services. This is when traditional street-side banks started considering ideas to deliver restricted online bank services to cut down the cost of operations. When these efforts proved beneficial and were acknowledged by all, numerous banks ideate to create their own cyber presence with newly designed website featuring the various services like opening new accounts online, necessary form download and processing loans. This has equally affected the hiring process for the professionals in the banking sector.

Apart from the banking examinations that one need to qualify, career in the banking for fresher requires technology experts. The Digital banking is becoming increasingly popular, it is necessary to survey factors affect their customer views, in a systematic way. Thus, the factors affecting customer satisfaction in the internet banking system need to be investigated in further studies. On the other hand, cause and effect relationships of these factors can impact on knowing internet banking customers' point of view and improve internet banking quality services. Building long-term relationships with customers has become a critical strategy for most financial institutions in today's competitive financial markets. The banking industry must develop profitable, long-term relationships with its customers in order to survive in the competitive retail banking environment. Several studies reveal that a bank's profitability is closely associated with customer loyalty and retention which is based on customer relationship.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the role of digitization in Indian banking.
2. To study the challenges of digital banking in India.
3. To study the Innovations in Digital Banking
4. To study the factors affect the scope of digital banking in India.

Research Methodology

The present study is descriptive in nature and is based on secondary data. The data has been extracted from various sources like research articles, publications from Government of India, various bulletins of RBI and authenticated websites.

Role of Digitization in Indian Banking

Banks in India as a whole were very reluctant to adopt the changes brought about by technological advancement. A number of factors brought about the mechanization and digitization in banking industry in India. The putting in place standard cheque encoders was the first step forward in digital transformation in banking. Magnetic Ink Character Recognition (MICR) helps in the sorting and processing of cheques with each bank branch having an MICR code. The next step was more of a necessity than an innovation. Banking is a respective job and therefore a labor intensive one where the worker is prone to making mistakes. In order to minimize errors and speed up the process, banks began using computer technology with standard personal computers and then set up their own local are networks (LAN). As the networks grew and banks began to connect together, Core banking came into being. Centralized Online Real time Exchange (CORE) banking thus allowed customers to perform financial transactions and access their account from any of the participating bans branches. These services made it easier for customers to operate their account and slowly led to the coining of the phrase: Anytime, Anywhere Banking". Then Automated Teller Machine (ATMs) arrived on the scene and electronic fund transfers were made possible. Online banking and Tele banking made their appearance in the 2000's and different modes of online fund transfers were instituted like Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS),

Immediate Payment System (IMPS). National Electronics Fund Transfer (NEFT) and National Electronic Clearing Service (NECS). Recent years have seen the growth in mobile banking services and other innovative services online. The role of digitization of banking in India that began in the 1980's has certainly come a long way.

Factors Affect the Scope of Digital Banking in India

- A. **Education:** A lack of knowledge about banking in itself is a hurdle. Many parts of India still struggle with very low literacy rate. The lack of knowledge about computers and the use of the internet is a challenge.
- B. **Training:** There is much resistance from within the banking industry itself. Employees are not trained in the use of innovative technology. They are unable to utilize different features of digital banking.
- C. **Fear:** There are a number of unfounded fears individuals have about the use of the internet. Cases of fraud are often increases and this adds to the fear factor, resulting in a number of ill informed customers being nervous to use digital banking.

Challenges of Digital Banking in India

1. Internet connection and a smart device such as mobile phone, tablet or personal computer is a prerequisite to use these services.
2. The digital literacy in India is still very low. According to the Internet and Mobile Association of India Report (IAMAI), 2016, Approximately 40% population is living below poverty line, illiteracy rate is not more than 25-30% and digital literacy is almost no-existent among more than 90% of India's population.
3. Security of user's information has been a matter of concern since the inception of electronic transactions and the same may hamper their adoption as well.
4. Difficulty in understanding the usage of the digital banking services. Senior citizens preferring the traditional banking systems and people who are not tech-savvy are more prone to this difficulty. According to a report on Encashing on Digital: Financial Services by 2020, 33% of banked population is not using digital banking as they find it complex to understand and operate .
5. According to the same report, 23% of banked population feel that digital banking services lack transparency in the form of hidden transaction charges.

Innovations in Digital Banking

1. Automated Teller Machines (ATMs)

Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) also known as an automated banking machine (ABM) is an electronic telecommunications device that enables the customers of a bank / financial institution to

perform financial transactions, particularly cash withdrawal, without the need for a human cashier, clerk or bank teller. The other functions performed by an ATM are check deposit, printing of receipts, balance enquiry, generating PIN, Passbook printing and so on.

2. National Automated Clearing House (NACH)

NACH is the centralized web-based payment solution that helps the banks, corporate sectors, government and other financial institutions to handle bulk payments. High volume transactions such as dividend and salary pay by the corporate, subsidies and pensions payment by the government and such can be easily done through NACH. The system will also assist the financial institutions and corporate to receive high volume payments as well. High volume payments that consist of water, electricity, telephone bills, loan amounts, EMIs, mutual fund investments payments can be received through NACH solution. The system is launched by National Payment Corporation of India, also known as NPCI.

3. Credit and Debit Cards

This facility promote cashless purchasing i.e. enables the customers to purchase goods without holding cash. A credit card allows the customer to borrow money within settled limits and Credit Card Company charged certain amount of interest for the money being used for purchasing by the customer. However, the debit card linked directly to the customer account and the money debited automatically from the customer account on every purchase.

4. National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT)

National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) system is a nation-wide system that facilitates individuals, firms and corporate to electronically transfer funds from any bank branch to any individual, firm or corporate having an account with any other bank branch in the country.

The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) maintains this payment network. NEFT system is a funds transfer mechanism where transfer of money takes place from one bank to another on a deferred net settlement basis. For being part of the NEFT funds transfer network, a bank branch has to be NEFT-enabled. Indian Financial System Code (IFSC) is required to perform a transaction using NEFT. IFSC code identifies a specific branch of a bank.

5. Mobile banking

Mobile banking is using mobile phone to access bank account; receive debit/credit alerts and statements via SMS; check balances and recent transactions by browsing a simple mobile enabled website; conduct basic operations via a menu; or transfer funds and pay bills using an application on a smart phone • Mobile can fundamentally change the

retail banking experience and strengthen customer-bank relationships.

Benefits of Digital Banking

1. Customer Service:

With internet freely available everywhere, all a customer needs to access his account is a device and internet connectivity. It saves him time and expense as he no longer has to travel to a bank to carry out transactions. He does not have to wait in unending queues only to find that he will have to go to a different counter to get his job done. Online services make it possible for him to sit in the comfort of his home or office, or in fact even in a vehicle while travelling, and carry out transactions without having to wait for anything.

2. 24x7 Availability:

The customer is able to check his bank records anytime he wishes and a number of banking services are available to him round the clock. Transferring money is easier, quicker, and safer.

3. Time Constraint:

A number of services required waiting for considerable periods. Banks had boards put up at their branches specifying the time required for different services. Even simply cashing a cheque took time. But with digital banking it is instant, with no time constraints.

4. Online Bill Payments:

This is a feature that saves customers a lot of time and expense. Customers do not have to carry cash and queue up to pay their utility bills or other bills.

5. Lower Overheads:

Digital banking has drastically reduced the operating costs of banks. This has made it possible for banks to charge lower fees for services and also offer higher interest rates for deposits. Lower operating costs have meant more profits for the banks.

6. Banking Benefits:

With the increased convenience of anytime, anywhere banking, the number of customers has increased for banks. Human error in calculations and recordkeeping is reduced, if not eliminated. With records of every transaction being maintained electronically, it is possible to generate reports and analyze data at any point, and for different purposes.

Conclusion

With the increasing usage of smart phones, digitalization of banking sector is inevitable to catch up the increasing expectations of the world. There is no doubt that the Banking Sector in India has become more competitive with the advent of digitization and the Digital India Program for ensuring better customer service, thereby attaining the goal of a cash-less economy. From the study it can be concluded that the digital innovations are creating a new picture of banking services all together. The digitization in banking has started

shifting the paradigm of cash and paper based banking to cashless and paperless banking. However, there is still a long way to cover by encountering the challenges with possible solutions and encasing the available opportunities. However, Indian banking sector will have to overcome many challenges to make digital banking pervasive. Internet connectivity and associated digital infrastructure is to be ensured for making the digital dream a reality. Then there is the risk of cyber threats which may cause significant disruptions in the banking services apart from risks related to sensitive customer information and internet frauds. It will be interesting to see how these challenges are dealt with by the banking sector.

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